

SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO HARNESS THE POTENTIAL OF CRM SECONDARY SOURCES ON THE EXAMPLE OF RED MUD

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Introduction

Red mud – an alkaline, iron and aluminium rich material – is a by-product resulting from alumina extraction by the Bayer process from bauxite. Often it is regarded as waste, but may rather be a potentially valuable resource of critical raw materials (CRMs) and other elements [1]. Spillage of disposed red mud may pose considerable risks to the local environment due to its alkalinity (pH usually ranging from 10 to 13), high sodium concentration ($>50 \text{ g L}^{-1}$), fine grained nature, and the release of metals and metalloids (e.g., Al, As, Cr, Mo, and V) to the soil-water environment [2]. There are many applications which have been investigated in the context of red mud reuse: as a stabilization material in building construction [3] or for improvement of acidic sulphate soils [4], for instance. As for other secondary sources, CRM extraction efficiencies may depend on a number of variables (e.g. acid strength, contact time, slurry concentration, etc.) that may be interdependent. This results in a high number of experiments to be conducted. In addition, some CRM are orders of magnitude more expensive than others and may drive economic feasibility though low concentrated. In consequence, considering total extraction yields (e.g. g/ton) may be misleading in terms of feasibility. Here, we developed an experimental design approach to determine optimal conditions for CRMs extraction. Instead of maximizing the extraction of a number of selected metals, the maximal economic potential for all metals extracted (total metal extracted \times economic value of the respective metal) was chosen as the application relevant response variable.

Materials and Methods

A design of experiment approach (Design Expert 8 Software) was used to strictly limit the number of experiments and to eventually derive an empirical model describing the data within the experimental conditions (0.5–6 M HCl, 1–24 hours, 50–80 °C, slurry concentration 10–100 g L⁻¹). The response surface reduced quadratic model considered both linear effects and interaction effects between HCl concentration, contact time, temperature, and slurry concentration. Total economic potential of extracted CRM was calculated as the sum of the economic value multiplied by the amount of respective element extracted. Economic values (for pure elements) were taken from USGS [5].

Results

All linear effects of the four tested factors had a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) effect on the total economic value. Furthermore, the two-factor interactions between HCl concentration and contact time, HCl concentration and slurry concentration, contact time and temperature, and temperature and slurry concentration were significant ($p \leq 0.05$). In addition, the quadratic effects of HCl concentration and temperature were also significant ($p \leq 0.05$) (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Two-factor interactions on the total economic value of extracted elements. Factors that are not shown in the graphs were held constant at the predicted optimal values (details in text) [6].

In contrast to any previous study, here also minor effects became clearly visible when one considers the maximal economic value of CRM extracted instead of considering a limited number of single elements. For instance, the effect of temperature may indeed be hard to distinguish for certain (easily acid available) elements (REE in Figure 1A), using the maximal economic value of a high number of

elements allowed to identify an optimum at intermediate temperatures (Figure 1B). Certainly the maximal economic value is not to be seen as a value that can actually be recovered (since based on pure, refined metals), however it allows to weighted consideration also of minor amounts of CRM, if they are of high economic value. Further, opposite effects (i.e. one set of element being more whereas another set of element being less efficiently extracted) are considered maximizing the overall value. Optimal conditions maximizing the economic potential were predicted for 5.60 M HCl, 24 h contact time, 73.4 °C, and 100 g L⁻¹ slurry concentration. Indeed, experimentally determined economic potential corresponded well (96 % of predicted) to the predictions, allowing a maximum recovery of 40.95 ± 0.90 US \$ t⁻¹. The studied Hungarian red muds were relatively low in CRM concentrations and thus feasible CRM recovery appears unfavourable. Nevertheless, the systematic approach (design of experiment using the max. economic potential as variable) developed here allows straightforward transfer to any other secondary source.

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